

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE STUDY HABITS OF THE STUDENTS
FROM MILITARY SCHOOL AND ENGLISH MEDIUM SCHOOL**

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Abstract: *The present research deals with A comparative Study of the Study habits of the Students from military School and English Medium School*

Students. The samples comprise 120 School Students by using Purposive sampling technique. The tools used for present research are M. N. Palsane and Anuradha Sharma The data was analyzed using t.

Findings *There is no significant difference in study habits between Military and English medium school students. (Military and English medium school students have similar Study habits.)*

Keywords: *study habits.*

Introduction: Teacher plays a significant role in drawing the best potentialities from the students to nourish a good study habit. Again the exploration of knowledge claims the regular study of books in different, so the students should have proper study habits. Some students read newspapers for getting more and more information and some read only prescribed books to prepare for their examination. No one can deny the importance of teaching and learning in the whole process of education. This process can only become successful when teachers fully know their subject matter and effectively communicate it to students and while students have a clear view of their abilities, have good study habits and are able to use effective study skills. Study habits are defined as those techniques, such as summarizing, note taking, outlining, and mind mapping or locating material which learners employ to assist themselves in the efficient learning of the material and hand. The term "study habit" implies a sort of more or less permanent method of studying.

According to the Boods Dictionary of education, "study habits are the tendency of pupil to study when the opportunities are given, the pupil's way of studying whether systematic or unsystematic, efficient or inefficient. There is no doubt that these complain evidently point to one fact. That is, lack of effective study habits. It is this problem, the researcher wishes to investigate as it appears to be one of the root causes of the dwelling standard of our educational system today. The present research is meant to find out whether there is difference in the military school and English Medium school Student study habits.

Need of Research - Need is the origin of invention the same is applicable for this research. Today the quality is considered more, so as in education also. Students grapple with many issues in these lines, and because of all of the competing things it's hard to concentrate on studying.

Too many people look at studying as a necessary task, not an enjoyment as opportunity to learn. Researcher something matters almost as much as what we do.

The important factor to consider when student study is students learning style. Students learn best in different ways. Some students learn better when they read something a teacher's explanation. Yet other students are visual learners that need to watch demonstrations as look at pictures.

Identifying students learning style will help to customize students study habits so that we get the best possible result.

Statement of the Problem A comparative Study of the Study habits of the Students from military School and English Medium School

Definition of Research Problems

Conceptual Definition

Study Habits:

- Good study habits lead to good academic record and bad study-habits lead to poor academic record as there is direct relationship between study habits and academic achievement.

Operational Definition

1. **Military school** - Military school is a school which provides formal residential education of military rules for 5th and 10th standard and situated in Akola Tehsil of Akola district as decided by researcher.

2. **English Medium school** – English Medium School is a school which provides formal education and learning teaching medium of English for 5th and 10th standard and situated in Akola Tehsil of Akola district as decided by researcher.

3. **Student** - Secondary school is schools which provide formal education for 9th std. and situated in Akola, Tehsil of Akola district as decided by researcher and boys and girls learning in this school is Student.

4. **Study Habits:** A score of boys and girls Military and English Medium school student in standardize test Study habits scale by M. N. Palsane and Anuradha Sharma indicates Study habits.

Objectives For the present research the researcher have decided the following objectives.

1. A study of Study habits of boys and girls in Military school.
2. A study of Study habits of boys and girls of in English medium.
3. A study of Study habits of boys-girls Military school and English medium school students.

Hypotheses- For the present research the researcher have decided the following Null hypotheses.

1. There is no significant difference between study habits of boys and girls in military school.
2. There is no significant difference between study habits of boys and girls in English medium school.
3. There is no significant difference in study habits between boys- girl’s military and English medium school students.

Methodology of the study: Descriptive survey method has been used for the study

Sample -A sample is a small proportion of a population selected for observation and analysis by observing the characteristics of the population from which it is drawn. Thus, sampling is the process of selecting the fractional part from the universe. The ideal sampling should be such that error of estimation is minimized. 300 military and English medium schools students included in population. Out of them, about 40 percent students were selected for the sample of the study. Purposive sampling Method was used to select the sample from population.

Table 1.1 shows the sample of military school and English medium school students selected through the akola tehsil.

Students	Military school	English medium school	Total
Boys	30	30	60
Girls	30	30	60
Total			120

Tools of Research

Study habits scale:- This is a standardized study habit inventory gives by M. N. Palsane and Anuradha Sharma. The study habits of the individual cover mainly the reading habits, learning techniques, memory, time schedule, physical conditions, examination and evaluation etc

Statistical techniques - The obtained data was analyzed by using the Statistical techniques viz. correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation: The collected data is subjected to statistical analysis and the results obtained are as given below.

Data Analysis and Interpretation In the attempting to assess the Study Habits of the Military school and English medium school students the whole sample data analysis was done and table 1.1 presents the overall Mean, SD value of the students.

Table over all study habits of the students

Students		N	Mean	SD
Military school	Boys	30	103.20	17.12
	Girls	30	106.10	16.55
English Medium	Boys	30	105.60	16.01
	Girls	30	107.68	16.20

As per Result of Administrating the Study habits Scale on a sample of 120 military and English medium school students in Akola tehsil. The following table 1.1 shows sample classification on the basis their study habits scores.

Table Classification of the students based on their study habits.

Scores	Interpretation	Military School Students	English Medium school Students
30-45	Highly unfavorable Study Habits	02	03
46-60	Unfavorable Study Habits	10	05
61-75	Neutral	30	20
76-99	Favorable Study Habits	10	25
100-150	Highly favorable Study Habits	08	07
Total		60	60

Figure : 1.1 Study Habits of Military school students

Figure : Study Habits of English Medium school students

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis no. 01: There is no significant difference between study habits of boys and girls in military school.

Table 1.3

Results of t -test between boys and girls of military school with respect to their study habits.

Military school	N	Mean	SD	df	Table 't'	Obtained 't'	Accept/ Rejected
Boys	30	103.20	17.12	58	2.00	0.67	Accepted
Girls	30	106.10	16.55				

- From the results of Table No.1.3, it can be seen that, the boys and girls military school do not differ significantly with respect to Study habits ($t=0.67, p>0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.
- On the basis of obtain't' value; we can say that, There is no significant difference between study habits of boys and girls in military school.
- Finding: Indicating that the boys and girls of military schools have similar Study habits.

Figure 1.3 Comparison of Mean of Study habits Scores of boys and girls in Military school.

Hypothesis no. 02: There is no significant difference between study habits of boys and girls in English medium school.

Table 1.4

Results of t -test between boys and girls of English medium school with respect to their study habits.

English Medium school	N	Mean	SD	df	Table 't'	Obtained 't'	Accept/ Rejected
Boys	30	105.60	16.01	58	2.00	0.50	Accepted
Girls	30	107.68	16.20				

- From the results of Table No. 1.4, it can be seen that, the boys and girls English medium school do not differ significantly with respect to Study habits ($t=0.50$, $p>0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.
- On the basis of obtain't' value; we can say that, There is no significant difference between study habits of boys and girls in English medium school.
- Finding: Indicating that the boys and girls of English medium schools have similar Study habits.

Figure Comparison of Mean of Study habits Scores of boys and girls in English medium school

Hypothesis no. 03: There is no significant difference in study habits between Military and English medium school students.

Table

Results of t -test between Military and English medium school students with respect to their study habits.

school	N	Mean	SD	df	Table 't'	Obtained 't'	Accept/ Rejected
Military School	60	104.65	16.83	118	1.98	0.46	Accepted
English Medium school	60	106.64	16.10				

- From the results of Table No. 1.4, it can be seen that, Military and English medium school students do not differ significantly with respect to Study habits ($t=0.46$, $p>0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.
- On the basis of obtain 't' value; we can say that, There is no significant difference in study habits between Military and English medium school students.
- Finding: Indicating that the Military and English medium school students have similar Study habits.

Figure 1.5
Comparison of Mean of Study habits Scores of Military and English medium school students.

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